

Making Decisions about Privacy in Tertiary Education Recommendation Systems in South Africa: Privacy Calculus in Action

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Abstract. Recommender Systems (RS) play a crucial role in managing information overload, particularly in fields such as education, where decisions have significant and long-term implications. This study investigates the impact of System Privacy Concerns constructs on privacy calculus and information disclosure decisions in a tertiary education setting within the South African context. We employ the Design Science Research (DSR) approach and mixed methods to enhance a model that integrates privacy calculus theory with a user-centric RS evaluation framework. Results from three iterative studies involving 719 university students indicate that System Privacy Concerns (SPC) influence RS Perceived Recommendation Quality (PRQ), Perceived System Usefulness (PSU), Overall Trust in the Recommender System (OTRS), and Interaction (INT). These findings highlight the delicate balance between user privacy concerns and the need for accurate, context-aware recommendations. This research provides a deeper understanding of privacy-sensitive RS design, offering developers and tertiary institutions valuable insights into students' privacy-related decision-making processes when using educational RS.

Keywords: Recommender Systems, User Privacy, Privacy calculus

1 Introduction

Recommender systems (RS) algorithms employ innovative methods to match students' interests and abilities with relevant courses, thereby reducing the likelihood of misguided choices and frustration by analysing large datasets to provide personalised recommendations that assist students in making informed decisions [1, 2]. RS unlocks focused, data-driven choices that boost student performance and retention by navigating large course handbooks and narrowing down alternatives based on individual preferences and needs [2]. As a result of the information overload problem in technologies, users find it more challenging to discover the correct information at the right moment, and RS have developed as a contributor towards solving this problem [3]. One of RS's primary purposes is to assist users in filtering and easily finding information in large databases [4]. As users struggle with the paradox of choice, where too many options lead to inefficient decision-making, RSs have proved to be helpful

for users in decision-making [5]. RS helps manage the problem of information overload by assisting users in making informed choices based on their personal data [6]. In the education domain, particularly in systems that recommend tertiary institutions and qualifications, students' choices driven by RS have long-term implications for their educational outcomes and career trajectories. Therefore, for RS to provide meaningful recommendations, users are required to provide sufficient personal and often sensitive, confidential data (e.g., biographical information, academic performance, household income) in real-life settings, ensuring accurate and context-aware recommendations. Studies on privacy reveal that many users are uneasy about sharing demographic information and have a negative perception of being monitored to collect contextual information [7].

The interaction between the users and RS for quality recommendations could drive social good in the education domain towards an equitable future in South Africa, however, this type of interaction necessitates careful engagement with ethical issues, such as data privacy, which arise alongside education RS innovations. This study aims to enhance the model proposed in Knijnenburg and Kobsa's (2013), addressing the limitations of the paper concerning behaviours related to privacy within a specific domain, education. This study conducts a user experiment in a real-life setting, rather than a lab experiment based on RS mock-ups.

This study was inspired by the unforeseen and evolving relationships identified in a related and ongoing evaluation study of education RS quality. The researchers observed several significant relationships associated with students' system privacy concerns during the initial data collection and analysis of the study iterations. The unexpected attitude of students towards their data privacy, alongside their lack of concern about system privacy when using an educational RS that benefitted them positively, prompted an observation and treatment of privacy concerns, which were explored in subsequent data collection iterations and analyses. Through this study, we attempt to answer the question: How do system privacy concerns mediate the processes behind users' privacy calculus and influence their information disclosure decisions in tertiary education RS? This study aims to extend the privacy decision-making model in [7], specifically within tertiary education RS, and address its limitations regarding real-life application and domain specificity. To answer the main research question, the DSR iterative approach was employed to construct a model that investigates the relationship between various constructs and SPC, aiming to contribute to an improved model that integrates privacy calculus theory and the RS user studies framework for RS developers and institutions.

2 Related work

2.1 Career Guidance and Decision Making in South Africa

Career Guidance, a vital topic in the Life Orientation curriculum for high schools in South Africa, is important for enabling students to make informed career decisions. A school-based Career Guidance program enables learners to maximise their earning potential, adapt to change, and recognise and utilise available opportunities [8]. Career Guidance is most effective when students align their interests with potential career

paths. This supportive environment enables individuals to showcase their skills and talents, resulting in significant success and job satisfaction [9]. In the 12th grade in South Africa, students make choices regarding their post-secondary career paths, whether that involves pursuing further education or seeking employment. The emergence of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have enabled Career Guidance services to be offered online. As an emerging trend, these services are provided through RS-enabled technologies, where RS-generated content is considered capable of managing career decision-making data [2]. In South Africa, the students' access to these tools may vary according to the school's quintile. The school quintile denotes the socio-economic or performance-based classification of a student's school. The National Department of Education (DBE) categorises public schools into five quintiles, with quintile 1 representing the poorest and quintile 5 the least poor. Users from higher-quintile schools may have greater technological exposure, which shapes their familiarity, acceptance, and usage of educational technologies [10, 11].

2.2 Information Disclosure Research on the Internet

Research on information disclosure explores the elements that can affect the amount of information users choose to share by viewing information disclosure as a decision-making challenge, where the individual must weigh various uncertain outcomes [7]. Privacy calculus theory (see Figure 1) posits that users disclose personal data based on a perceived risk-benefit analysis, influencing their willingness to engage with online services [10, 11]. Decisions regarding individual privacy are frequently characterised as a calculation where personal data is exchanged for specific benefits, often called privacy calculus [11]. Privacy concerns have become especially prominent since technology service providers might have access to more potentially sensitive data [11]. To understand information disclosure decisions regarding the data and personal information used by users on mobile applications, Figure 1 provides a theoretical framework that hypothesises that a trade-off between perceived privacy risks and perceived benefits shapes users' decisions to disclose personal information [10]. Higher perceived risks reduce disclosure intentions, while greater perceived benefits increase them. Privacy concerns indirectly affect these intentions by amplifying risks and diminishing benefits. Although intentions influence actual disclosure behaviour, the accuracy and honesty of disclosed information often moderate this relationship [10].

Fig. 1. Privacy calculus core theory

2.3 Existing Recommender Systems User Studies Frameworks

Research on privacy decision-making often focuses on privacy as a personal trait or variable influencing disclosure behaviour and rarely compares the two [7]. Additionally, the impact of personal attributes and system variables on information sharing varies significantly across different systems. Therefore, a unified approach to studying privacy decisions, which integrates privacy-related concepts, can potentially cover this gap [7]. Knijnenburg's (2012) user-centric evaluation framework integrates both personal and system attributes that influence user experience. This study employs a framework based on Knijnenburg & Kobsa's (2013) privacy concepts, emphasising SPC as a critical personal attribute that impacts RS interaction. Figure 2 outlines these integrations, highlighting the specific constructs and directional relationships that can be explored.

Fig. 2.: The framework for user-centric evaluation of RSs populated with the system privacy research concepts [7].

In line with the argument that the impact of personal attributes and system variables on information sharing varies greatly among systems, this study identified a gap in the literature in that there is a lack of a theory-based, real-life-tested framework for understanding how system privacy concerns mediate the processes behind users'

privacy calculus and influence their information disclosure decisions in domain-specific RS focusing on education. This paper addresses this gap by attempting to answer the question: How do system privacy concerns mediate the processes behind users' privacy calculus and influence their information disclosure decisions in tertiary education RS?

3 Method

This study was conducted using a Design Science Research (DSR) methodology with three iterative cycles of artefact refinement, adopting a mixed-methods approach to explore the research problem from users' perspectives. Employing mixed methods offers several advantages, primarily by providing more detailed and nuanced data through the integration of qualitative and quantitative patterns [12]. This study collected data using questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The survey instrument included items measuring perceived recommendation quality, usefulness, overall trust in the recommender system, satisfaction, and privacy concerns. Each construct was assessed using multiple statements on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree). To focus on and improve the quality of results for the local context, this study examined participants from South Africa only and asked a series of survey-based testing questions. In the combined three iterations, 719 post-secondary students with a minimum of six to ten months of university experience completed the questionnaires for this study, having selected their tertiary education paths through the educational RS while in high school. Furthermore, 26 students were interviewed for better insights into the quantitative data. The ontological stance adopted by the researchers in this study is pragmatism. A pragmatic philosophical perspective holds that reality is significant insofar as it has a practical effect on ideas, where knowledge is vital for facilitating the successful completion of specific actions [13]. Given this research's pragmatic focus, the adopted mixed-methods approach to data gathering effectively garnered both qualitative and quantitative insights necessary to understand students' experiences related to privacy in the education RS.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the privacy questions from the three iterations

Privacy Concerns	Count	Mean	Std	Min	25%	50%	75%	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Concerns of Data Disclosure	719	2.228	1.411	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	5.0	0.821	-0.643
Privacy Invasion	719	1.561	1.045	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	5.0	2.034	3.424
Confidence in Privacy Respect	719	4.420	1.069	1.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	-2.069	3.525
Data Sharing Comfort	719	1.848	1.255	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	5.0	1.366	0.684
Confidentiality Respect	719	4.428	1.170	1.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	-2.098	3.160

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used as the integrative statistical procedure for analysing the online survey results. SEM is an integrative statistical procedure because it simultaneously tests the measurement model and all hypotheses [14]. SEM allows researchers to model and estimate intricate interactions among multiple dependent and independent variables, and consequently, this technique improves the precision of measuring theoretical concepts [15].

4 Research hypothesis

Drawing on the user experience framework [16] and the logic of privacy calculus [6, 10], which suggests that higher perceived privacy risk reduces perceived benefits, we hypothesised that higher system privacy concerns would negatively impact users' perceived RS benefits and behaviours. Accordingly, the following five hypotheses were formulated:

- H1: System Privacy Concerns will have a negative effect on Perceived Recommendation Quality
- H2: System Privacy Concerns will negatively affect Perceived System Usefulness
- H3: System Privacy Concerns will have a negative effect on Overall Satisfaction
- H4: System Privacy Concerns will negatively affect Overall Trust in the Recommendation System
- H5: System Privacy Concerns will negatively and significantly influence users' Interaction with the Recommendation System

5 Results

To understand the research's findings regarding the influence of SPC on PQR, PSU, OS, OTRS, and INT. It is imperative to provide a contextual explanation of the Objective Systems Aspects (OSA) according to the [16] framework to better understand the constructed relationship with SPC in the RS usage by the participants. The OSAs, which are the primary drivers of the tertiary education RS studied in the research, are the algorithm, the recommendation set composition, and the preference input data.

- Algorithm: Despite the research interest in RS, there is a notable lack of knowledge on how algorithm accuracy affects user experience [12]. In this study, we examined a real-life perspective by evaluating the impact of the RS algorithm's perception beyond theoretical lab experiments. In the studied education RS, students log in to the application with a specific Choice Goal (CG) concerning tertiary education qualification and institution selection and are thereafter asked for invasive personal data ranging from biographical data, family household income and detailed academic performance to generate context-aware recommendations for post-secondary education opportunities.
- Recommendation set composition: Another critical aspect of the OSA is the composition of the recommendation set presented to the user. The education RS that

was studied presents recommendations based on the student's CG and academic performance. In the first iteration, the students were presented with seven tertiary institution recommendations, with each institution showing three related qualifications where students stood the best chance of qualifying based on the Grade 11 results and the institutions' Admission Point Score (APS). Thereafter, in the third iteration, the students were presented with eleven institutions and thirty-three related qualifications.

- Preference input data: The convergence of the algorithm and interface occurs during the process of eliciting preferences. The Content-Based Filtering (CBF) technique recommends items based on the user's explicit preferences or implicit preferences, derived from the user's selection history or past preferences. The studied RS uses a CBF technique, where the matching of the students' attributes (situational characteristics, career interests, institutional interests, study geography preference and academic performance) is considered and stored to recommend qualifications and institutions that align with the user's interests. The core CBF student item selection works as follows:
 - Step 1: Creation of a user account with personal and family biographic data
 - Step 2: Selection of the student's school, grade, and Grade 11 subjects
 - Step 3: Confirmation of academic performance from a valid school report
 - Step 4: Elicitation of the career choices and career goal confirmation
 - Step 6: Confirmation of the preferred institutions and qualifications
 - Step 7: Monitoring of the feedback
 - Step 8: Student utility feedback once they have completed high school

From the user's perspective, the SPC was evaluated over three iterations, and the following results were obtained as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Path Coefficients and Significance Levels of SEM in Iteration 3. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, Insignificant = $p \geq .0$

Relationship	Estimate	Bootstrap Mean	Bootstrap SD	T-Stat	Significance	2.5% CI	97.5% CI
SPC → PRQ [H1]	0.3484	0.3480	0.0453	7.6959	***	0.2610	0.4368
SPC → PSU [H2]	0.1240	0.1237	0.0231	5.3642	***	0.0843	0.1739
SPC → OS [H3]	0.0648	0.0655	0.0344	1.8840	-	-0.0009	0.1329
SPC → OTRS [H4]	0.1124	0.1127	0.0407	2.7596	**	0.0362	0.1918
SPC → INT [H5]	0.0488	0.0494	0.0210	2.3184	*	0.0087	0.0915

Overall, most relationships between SPC and the other constructs were positive rather than negative. Significant paths [H1, H2, H4, H5] show positive coefficients, whereas H3 was non-significant. Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between SPC and the PRQ, PSU, OTRS, and INT using the [6] framework. Within this context of education RS usage, some constructs that might be aggregated as SPC might correlate with greater RS attentiveness and engagement, leading to higher perceived system quality, usefulness, overall trust in the recommender system, and interaction. Additionally, subtle variations in question wording or socioeconomic factors such as school quintile

may lead students who are highly engaged with privacy questions to respond more positively overall. The discussion section enhances understanding of these results by providing additional insights from student interviews, which further clarify the meaning of the positive coefficients.

Fig. 3 : The framework for user-centric evaluation of RSs populated with the constructs tested in this study. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, Insignificant = $p \geq .0$

6 Discussion

This section aims to discuss the research hypothesis and support the claims using collected quantitative data, interviews from students (S) and existing theories from the literature. The section examines each hypothesis in detail and attempts to investigate the reasons behind the positive coefficients through direct student feedback, including interviews. Privacy calculus theory frames our exploration of SPC's role in education RS, especially regarding perceived benefits versus privacy risks.

H1. System Privacy Concerns will have a negative effect on Perceived Recommendation Quality. The gathered quantitative data does not support the hypothesised negative effect on PRQ. Instead, the results indicate a positive influence of SPC on PRQ, which contradicts some aspects of the Privacy Calculus theory [10]. Quantitative findings reveal a path coefficient of $\beta = 0.3484$ ($p < 0.001$) in the third iteration of the study. The descriptive statistics for “Confidence in Privacy Respect” ($M = 4.420$) and “Confidentiality Respect” ($M = 4.428$) exhibit high mean scores, underscoring robust trust in the application’s privacy measures. Qualitative interviews reinforce these insights, with most students reporting minimal apprehension about data misuse, citing password-protected access and the RS school's endorsement. S1 mentioned that “I wasn’t concerned... I didn’t see any need to be worried”. Even those

initially wary became reassured over time once they realised privacy safeguards were in place in the RS, where S16 commented, “I was sceptical... but at the same time, I was willing to take the risk.” Although some scepticism lingered among a minority of students, the overall consistency of positive relationships indicates that the perceived and experienced RS safeguards enhance the perceived quality of the recommendations by the students. The results show that the RS effectively aligns users’ privacy expectations with the recommendations provided.

H2: System Privacy Concerns will negatively affect Perceived System Usefulness. The research results do not support the hypothesised negative effect on PSU. Instead, they indicate a positive influence of SPC on PSU, highlighting how privacy features can enhance users’ perceptions of the system’s value in supporting tertiary and qualifications decisions. The SEM results for H2 show a significant relationship, with a path coefficient of $\beta = 0.1240$, suggesting that higher SPC align with higher perceived usefulness. Descriptive data similarly demonstrate strong confidence in the app’s privacy measures ($M = 4.420$ for “Confidence in Privacy Respect” and $M = 4.428$ for “Confidentiality Respect”), underscoring a group of students who see robust safeguards against misuse. Interview findings reinforce this perspective, revealing how privacy measures shaped students’ sense of the RS’s overall usefulness. For example, S10 explained, “The App gave me the exact match with my marks on how I was doing because I used my marks. The App showed me the specific qualifications that were relevant to me,” emphasising how a secure environment where confidential academic results contributed to more tailored, and useful recommendations. S14 also found the system both secure and useful, highlighting, “I trusted the app, and it helped me narrow down my course options. It is like it knew what I needed.” Likewise, S15 noted, “I never encountered any problems, so I never had any concerns about privacy,” while S11 highlighted the platform’s comparative reliability: “It is better than just Googling. Here, you know your information is safe, and the recommendations make sense for what you want.” These results reflect privacy calculus in action, where students weighed the potential risks of sharing their personal information against the tangible benefits of receiving accurate, personalised guidance. In this case, the advantage of accurate and reliable recommendations outweighed privacy reservations, thereby possibly explaining why higher levels of perceived privacy concern actually correlate with a stronger sense of the system’s usefulness.

H3: System Privacy Concerns will have a negative effect on Overall Satisfaction. Despite prior indications of significance, the final iteration reveals that the SPC relationship with OS is no longer statistically supported ($\beta = 0.0648$) in the third iteration of the DRS step. However, the positive direction suggests that mitigating privacy concerns may still contribute to overall satisfaction, even if it does not reach conventional significance levels. This sentiment is echoed by S26, who acknowledged initial wariness but felt reassured by the system’s benefits over time: “I was concerned...but then I realised it is helping us.” Such experiences align with the Privacy Calculus theory [11] and the Personalisation-Privacy Paradox, wherein students weigh potential risks against perceived utility, often discovering that the RS delivers sufficient value to alleviate privacy concerns. Considering the insignificance of the final path

coefficient, we cannot definitively conclude that privacy concerns directly influence user satisfaction in this explored context.

H4: System Privacy Concerns will negatively affect Overall Trust in the Recommendation System. The final iteration results do not support the hypothesised negative impact on OTRS. Instead, the path coefficient is $\beta = 0.1124$, with a T-statistic of 2.7596 ($p < 0.01$), demonstrating the opposite. This finding contrasts with earlier, inconclusive trends, underscoring a possible nuanced relationship that could reflect how strong privacy measures or transparent processes reassure students once they begin interacting with the RS. Qualitative insights further highlight why possible heightened SPC might translate into positive trust outcomes. S1 expressed minimal worry, attributing their confidence to the absence of perceived risk, while S10 emphasised the role of password security: “I have the password, so I did not think anyone could access my account,” thereby reinforcing their trust in the recommender system. S16 recounted feeling “sceptical” at first but acknowledged that continued usage and proven benefits eased those fears, and S26 similarly described how initial reservations faded as they discovered the RS truly aided their academic focus.

Although a few students retained some caution, the overall pattern, from both the SEM findings and student narratives, demonstrates that SPC, when sufficiently addressed by security features, can increase trust in the education RS. Thus, the final iteration’s evidence contradicts the negative hypothesis, showing a positive link between SPC and OTRS in this educational context.

H5: System Privacy Concerns will negatively and significantly influence users’ Interaction with the Recommendation System. Contrary to the expected negative effect, the final iteration shows a positive, but modest, relationship ($\beta = 0.0488$, T-stat = 2.3184, $p < 0.05$). While the coefficient has decreased from previous iterations, it remains significant, suggesting that students with higher SPC still engage with the RS, potentially due to the perception that privacy concerns are well-managed or outweighed by the system’s benefits. Descriptive data on privacy (“Privacy Invasion” $M = 1.561$, “Data Sharing Comfort” $M = 1.848$) confirm overall low concern, reinforcing the notion that such worries do not substantially deter system usage. Qualitative insights elaborate on this subtle connection. S1 admitted, “I was not quite aware of any privacy issues, and I did not think there was a need for me to feel worried,” showcasing how minimal privacy fears can facilitate confident interaction with the RS. Even students who initially hesitated, like S16, declared they were “willing to take the risk,” and S26 stated, “At first, I was concerned... but over time, I realised this helps children focus on studying and doing well.” Over time, these doubts diminished, suggesting a reciprocal relationship between privacy perceptions and continued RS interaction, potentially indicating that the more students used the system, the more they experienced its practical benefits, thereby alleviating their concerns.

Despite the positive direction, the relatively low coefficient may indicate that privacy concerns are only one of multiple factors influencing interaction. S11 summed this up by emphasising greater comfort with the application compared to other platforms: “I felt more comfortable sharing documents with the RS compared to other websites.” In this way, the final iteration’s results confirm that addressing privacy issues can facilitate interaction, contrary to the original negative hypothesis.

Overall, the results challenge traditional privacy calculus predictions, revealing nuanced relationships where enhanced SPC aligns with increased user engagement and trust, likely due to perceived effective privacy protections. Qualitative interviews support these findings, showing how explicit privacy features strengthen user trust and RS value perceptions. These findings highlight the Personalisation-Privacy Paradox, where users accept privacy risks for significant personalisation benefits.

Design implications for RS developers include embedding clear privacy assurances and effectively communicating data usage within RS interfaces, which significantly enhances user trust and interaction.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

This section draws conclusions based on the data collected in the broader study and the preceding discussion, addressing the core question: How do System Privacy Concerns mediate the processes behind users' privacy calculus and influence their information disclosure decisions in tertiary education RS. In line with the gap identified from literature [6], our study sought to extend existing privacy calculus theory into a specific educational domain, focusing on real-world usage rather than lab-based RS evaluation. Through iterative data collection and analysis using the DSR method, we observed positive relationships between SPC and critical RS constructs such as PRQ, PSU, OTRS, and INT. While the direct effect of SPC on OS was not statistically significant in the final model, qualitative insights suggest that RS privacy safeguards and transparent data-handling practices promote student privacy reassurance, and as such, students are more willing to share sensitive information.

These findings underscore that when privacy measures and user trust are cultivated through password protection, clear privacy statements, and institutional endorsements, such as schools, students are more readily engaged with the education RS, aligning with Privacy Calculus theory and the Personalisation-Privacy Paradox. Although a subset of students initially expressed caution, most concerns diminished once they recognised the platform's tangible benefits. This process illustrates how privacy considerations, rather than impeding system use, can heighten perceived value if thoughtfully managed from a design perspective. These findings emphasise that educational RS designers must implement visible privacy safeguards and transparent data practices to foster user trust. Educational institutions should also recognise the necessity of clear privacy policies and governance to protect student data, which will promote broader adoption and confidence in these RS systems. Furthermore, from a socio-economic perspective, no evidence was found to demonstrate differential results based on the school quintile in the collected data. Therefore, the results, having explored the socio-economic perspective, have shown that the SPC behaviour has not changed despite the student's background.

By testing these relationships in an authentic tertiary education setting rather than a controlled laboratory, our study helps fill a gap in the literature. Although the direct influence of SPC on overall satisfaction did not reach statistical significance, qualitative interviews suggest that privacy measures may provide reassurance and foster long-term

contentment for many students. Ultimately, this research highlights the social good potential of education RS in South Africa, provided privacy elements are carefully integrated to mitigate students' concerns and strengthen their trust. However, this study has certain limitations. First, the sample was limited to a single educational context in South Africa, using a single RS, which may restrict generalisability to other domains or regions. Second, our data relied on self-reported perceptions at a single point in time of each iteration. Longitudinal studies tracking actual long-term usage would offer deeper insights into how privacy calculus decisions evolve. Future studies should address these limitations to validate and expand our findings.

Future research will refine our understanding of privacy-related decision-making in context-aware RSs, building on the [7] model and extending our iterative model. In particular, exploring individual traits and objective system factors may further elucidate why some students remain wary of RS privacy. Additional data may also facilitate testing the explanatory and predictive power of the model in socially diverse educational contexts, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive picture of privacy's role in fostering meaningful and trustworthy system interactions, potentially enriching both academic discourses on RS privacy and the practical design of privacy-sensitive education RS.

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